

TOP FIVE WAYS OF TEACHING ENGLISH EFFECTIVELY

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ANNOTATION

In this article, we are going to inform you about how we teach learners for different kind of languages like English, German, Turkish, Korean and so on. It is acknowledged that learning new languages have become an integral part of our life. Due to the fact that we would like to discuss what kind of interesting skills can impact language learners, and we will share with you TOP 5 ways during this research.

Keywords: technical resources, new acknowledgement, pre-test, post-test, skills, strategies, time-management.

In 21st century, there has been a significant increase on different fields, especially, learning new languages. This is because the most majority of students addicted to going somewhere for travelling or business and this demands from them language skill in the first position. In presenting the profile of the learner, the book explores why students want to learn English, where they are learning it, how different learners are from each other, how motivation affects learning, and what it means to be an autonomous learner. The teacher's concern, thus, is how to teach effectively and consequently help 'provoke success'. One of the striking points Harmer makes has to do with what constitutes an effective teaching personality: 'We need to ask ourselves what kind of personality we want our students to encounter, and the decisions we take before and during lessons should help demonstrate that personality. It is a way of saying that what effective teaching begins with is a good teacher's decision and not something that happens by chance (either you have it or you do not!). The present study compares the effects of the cooperative jigsaw II method and traditional teacher-centred teaching method on improving vocabulary knowledge and active-passive voice in English as a foreign language for engineering students and the students' attitudes towards learning English. Jigsaw is a cooperative learning model that involves small groups of 5-6 students teaching each other subject matter with success dependent upon student cooperation. Sixty-six engineering students participated in the study and a pre-test-post-test control group experimental design are employed. The students are randomly assigned into two groups: an experimental group and a control group. The experimental group used cooperative Jigsaw II as an instruction method while the control group used traditional teacher-centred instruction. The groups were administered an achievement test, as a pre-post and delayed post-test. The results revealed statistically significant differences in favour of the experimental group on the dependent variables of improving vocabulary knowledge and learning active-passive voice in English. The attitude scale results showed that the cooperative learning experience had a significant positive effect on engineering students' attitudes towards learning English and promoted better interactions among students as well.

We can also inspire students in different ways giving some instructions and motivation:

Firstly, keep it simple when you are explaining something for them. This is one of the most important steps of teaching English and other foreign languages to beginner levels.

Secondly, always check for understanding if learners have a doubt for their thought. Activate their background knowledge. Recent research has shown that better comprehension occurs when students are engaged in activities that bridge their old knowledge with new skills.

Thirdly, give them task for practicing. In this process, learners cultivate their knowledge via doing new theme task. This helps them to learn something efficiently and effectively.

Fourthly, show, do not tell. Even you do not have enough time, you should give an instruction students through writing on black-board, white-board or smart-board. It may be helpful for them remember the theme clearly, looking examples given by you.

Fifthly, be positive and motivate them. Not be bored during the lesson because it affects not only learners' thoughts but also yours'. So, even on your darkest days always smile in the period of your class to broaden your students' horizon.

Create a supportive environment that appreciates diversity. It's important that students feel they can freely express themselves in an environment where their diverse backgrounds are respected and celebrated. Pair them up with a buddy, preferably a buddy they choose themselves and are comfortable working with and getting along with.

Advancements in technology have propelled the education sector in the last few decades. As the name suggests, the high tech approach to learning utilizes different technology to aid students in their classroom learning. Many educators use computers and tablets in the classroom, and others may use the internet to assign homework. The internet is also beneficial in a classroom setting as it provides unlimited resources. Teachers may also use the internet in order to connect their students with people from around the world.

These great language teachers understand that there is no quick fix that they can deploy to help students quickly become fluent in their target language. Instead, there are some common, evidence-based language teaching approaches which can help make a difference. As our language teaching software tools here at Sanako are designed to allow teachers to use which ever pedagogical method they wish, we thought it would be valuable for our customers and blog readers to have a good overview of different teaching approaches. This blog post therefore summarises 5 of the most notable approaches to language teaching. We hope that they will support language educators looking for some inspiration to improve their teaching practice.

It's worth noting that none of these approaches should be considered "the best" since every classroom, educator and student is different. Our advice is rather that educators should try them out, tailoring them to their specific context and reviewing the impact they have. Keep also in mind that these strategies can be adapted and combined in various ways to suit different learners, contexts, and educational goals. The most effective language teaching approach is often a mix of several strategies tailored to the needs of individual learners.

1. Communicative language teaching (CLT)

This approach is probably now the most popular teaching model for English language teaching globally. In part because it aims to put students in a variety of real-life situations, so that they can learn how to use their language skills to communicate in the real world.

Educators therefore tend to focus on fluency of communication rather than accuracy and lessons are more hands-on than theoretical. Interactive and relevant classroom activities characterise this approach along with the use of authentic source materials. Teachers are encouraged to provide the students with as much opportunity to give and receive meaningful communication as possible. The use of personal experience is also common in CLT classrooms.

2. Task-based language teaching (TBLT)

The focus of TBLT teaching is solely on the completion of a detailed task which interests and engages the learners. Learners use the language skills that they already have to complete the task and work through three distinct phases – a pre-task, the task itself and post-task. Students might, for example, be asked to deliver a presentation about an important environmental issue. In order to complete it, they will need to read / listen to source material, conduct internet research, as well as writing and delivering the presentation itself. Research suggests that students in TBLT classes are empowered and motivated because they 'own' the language and can control the nature of the task response.

3. Content and language integrated learning (CLIL)

The CLIL approach principally involves studying one subject (for example, biology, science or history) and learning a language, such as English, at the same time — effectively integrating the two subjects. The language teaching is organized around the demands of the first subject rather than that of the target language. So it's critically important to make sure that the integration is clear and that students are engaged. Having said that, the CLIL approach does create significant opportunities for cross-curricular working; it opens up language learning to a wider context and can be used to re-engage previously demotivated students.

4. Cooperative Language Learning (CLL)

Cooperative Language Learning or CLL forms part of a wider teaching approach known as Collaborative or Community Learning (CL). CLL seeks to make the maximum use of cooperative activities involving pairs and small groups of learners in the classroom. As such, it is a student-centered, rather than a teacher-centered, approach to language teaching. In the CLL classroom, all of the language learning activities are deliberately designed to maximise opportunities for social interactions. Students should accomplish tasks by interacting between themselves and talking / working together. The teacher's role is to act as a facilitator of and a participant in the learning tasks.

5. The Direct Method

In this language teaching approach, all teaching happens in the target language, forcing the learner to think and speak in that language. The learner does not use their native language in the classroom at all! As a result, students work out key grammar concepts by practicing the language and by building up their exposure to it. Standard classroom techniques for this approach include **Q+As**, conversation, reading aloud, writing and student self-correction.

At the end of my article, I should mention that our life is full of opportunities that we do not use. In our technological world, there is no cause to escape from learning. All methods that I have mentioned above play a crucial role in your learning time. As compared to other languages, learning English is the most priority and those of methods can enhance your skill more than you think. So, be careful and potential when you are cultivating your knowledge.

References:

1. Anantha Anilkumar. 13 The most effective teaching strategies. Third space learning.com
2. Eremy Harmer ELT Journal 62, 2008
3. (Case of Firat University, Turkey) MN Gömleksiz European journal of engineering education 32 (5), 613-625, 2007
4. Splashlearn.com
5. repository.iaincurup.ac.id
6. sanako.com. Language teaching strategies, tips for language teachers.

